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PROTEOMIC STUDIES OF CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF *EUPHORBIA HIRTA*

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ABSTRACT

The present research work was aimed to discover anti-viral and anti-dengue activity of the phytochemicals present in *Euphorbia hirta* using Molecular docking studies. In this research work, we have screened anti-dengue and anti-viral activity of 10 chemical constituents from *Euphorbia hirta* through docking studies, the target enzymes were chosen for the study is 3P54, 2V33, 5B1C, 4M9K and 5FC8 using Argus lab 4.0.1 software. Among the 10 screened compounds of *Euphorbia hirta*, shows best to moderate (-9.49194kcal/mol to -5.61913kcal/mol) binding energy and various bonding interactions against the targeted proteins. On the basis of docking study results, it can be concluded that chemical constituents of *Euphorbia hirta*, serve as promising chemical probes to design therapeutic agents with anti-dengue and antiviral properties.

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INTRODUCTION

Dengue is a neglected disease responsible for 22,000 deaths each year in areas where it is endemic. To date, there is no clinically approved dengue vaccine or antiviral for human beings, even though there have been great efforts to accomplish these goals. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that the annual global incidence of dengue is close to 390 million, a number nearly three times higher than the number of cases estimated by the same organization for 2009. The number of cases reported increased from 2.2 million in 2010 to 3.2 million in 2015. The year 2016 was characterized by large dengue outbreaks worldwide. The Region of the Americas region reported more than 2.38 million cases in 2016, where Brazil alone contributed slightly less than 1.5 million cases, In 2017 the Region of Americas have reported 50,172 cases of dengue fever, a reduction as compared with corresponding periods in previous years. The Western Pacific Region has reported dengue outbreaks in several Member States in the Pacific, as well as the circulation of DENV-1 and DENV-2 serotypes.^[1]

Increased urbanization along with substandard housing, unreliable water supply, and poor sanitation provide a suitable environment for vector proliferation in close proximity to human hosts.^[2] The disease has four viral serotypes (DENV 1–4), and its spectrum ranges from asymptomatic infection to dengue fever (DF), dengue hemorrhagic fever (DHF), and dengue shock syndrome (DSS), and may lead to patient death, all four serotypes of dengue virus are transmitted to humans by the *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes.^[3]

Several approaches have been used in the search for dengue antivirals such as screening of compounds against dengue virus enzymes and structure-based computational discovery. During the last decades, researchers have turned their attention to natural compounds, trying to identify compounds that can be used as dengue antivirals. Nature represents a vast reservoir of substances that can be explored with the aim of discovering new leads that can be either used directly as pharmaceuticals or can serve as lead structures that can be optimized towards the development of new antiviral agents against dengue. The present research work was aimed to discover anti-viral and anti-dengue activity of the chemical constituents present in *Euphorbia hirta* (figure: 1) using Molecular docking studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Figure: 1 Habitat of *Euphorbia hirta*.

Preparation of protein structure

The 3D structure of 3P54 (Crystal Structure of the Japanese Encephalitis Virus Envelope Protein, strain SA-14-14-2)^[4], 2V33 (High resolution crystal structure of domain III of E1 fusion glycoprotein of Semliki Forest Virus)^[5], 5B1C (Crystal structure of DEN4 ED3 mutant with L387I)^[6], 4M9K (NS2B-NS3 protease from dengue virus at pH 5.5)^[7] and 5FC8 (Mouse importin alpha: Dengue 3 NS5 C-terminal NLS peptide complex)^[8] viral and dengue proteins are used for the current study. The protein sequence was retrieved in the fasta format and the 3D structure was determined using CPH model server. All water molecules were removed and hydrogen atoms were added to the target protein molecule.

Preparation of the ligand structures

The ligands used for docking study were selected from the literature. The bioactive compounds those are mainly present in the *Euphorbia hirta* under Plantae Kingdom, Euphorbiaceae Family. *Euphorbia hirta* (sometimes called asthma-plant) is a plant tropical weed, possibly native to India. It is a hairy herb that grows in open grasslands, roadsides and pathways. It is widely used as a medicinal herb.^[9] The ligand structures were generated using the tool Chemskech. Three-dimensional optimizations of the ligand structures were done and saved as ‘.mol file’. Geometry optimizations of the ligands were performed according to the Hartree–Fock (HF) calculation method using ArgusLab 4.0.1 (Mark A. Thompson, Planaria Software LLC, Seattle, WA, USA, <http://www.arguslab.com>)^[10] software. The compounds included in the study are Flavonoids (Euphorbianin, leucocyanidol, camphol, quercitrin and quercitol), Polyphenol (Gallic acid, myricitrin, 3,4-di-O-galloylquinic acid, 2,4,6-tri-O-galloyl- D-glucose, 1,2,3,4,6-penta-O-galloyl-β- D-glucose),^[11] Tannins (Euphorbins A, B, C, D, E (11), Triterpenes and phytosterols (β-Amyrin, 24-methylenecycloartenol, and β-Sitosterol) Alkanes (Heptacosane, n-nonacosane).^[12] The bioactive compounds considered for the study are listed in Table 1.

Table: 1 Chemical constituent of *Euphorbia hirta* and their structures**Binding site prediction**

Q-SiteFinder^[13] (<http://www.bioinformatics.leeds.ac.uk/qsitfinder>) and PDB sum^[14] (<http://www.biochem.ucl.ac.uk/bsm/pdbsum>), are used for binding site prediction. It uses the interaction energy between the protein and a simple van der Waals probe to locate energetically favourable binding sites.

Protein-ligand docking using Argus Lab 4.0.1

Argus Lab is an electronic structure program that is based on the quantum mechanics. It predicts the potential energies, molecular structures; geometry optimization of structure, vibration frequencies of coordinates of atoms, bond length, and bond angle.

4M9K, 3P54, 2V33, 5FC8 and 5B1C protein was docked individually against the each bioactive compound from the leaves of *Euphorbia hirta* using ArgusLab^[10]. The interaction was carried out to find the favourable binding geometries of the ligand with the protein. Docking of the protein ligand complex was mainly targeted only to the predicted active site. Docking simulations were performed by selecting “ArgusDock” as the docking engine. The selected residues of the receptor were defined to be a part of the binding site. A spacing of 0.4 Å between the grid points was used and an exhaustive search was performed by enabling “High precision” option in Docking precision menu, “Dock” was chosen as the calculation type, “flexible” for the ligand, and the “AScore” was used as the scoring function. A maximum of 150 poses were allowed to be analyzed; binding site box size was set to 20 × 20 × 20 Å so as to encompass the entire active site.

The AScore function, with the parameters read from the AScore.prm file, was used to calculate the binding energies of the resulting docked structures¹⁵. All the compounds in the dataset were docked into the active site of the selected protein, using the same protocol. The docking poses saved for each compound were ranked according to their dock score function. The pose having the highest dock score was selected for further analysis.^[10]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Protein-Ligand interaction plays a significant role in structure based drug designing. In the present work, we have docked the chemical constituents of *Euphorbia hirta* with viral proteins 4 M9K, 3P54, 2V33, 5FC8 and 5B1C which is used as target for viral and dengue diseases. The Docking studies were carried out through ArgusLab^[11], based on the highest binding energy and various interactions; we predicted the active site of the protein by using Pdb-Sum server. Figures: 2–6 shows the binding poses of the Beta-amyryn. The experimental analysis shows that best docking pose of chemical constituents in *Euphorbia hirta* with targeted proteins are listed in Table 2.

Figure: 2 Binding pose of Beta- amyryn with 4M9K

Figure: 3 Binding pose of Beta- amyryn with 3P54.

Figure: 4 Binding pose of Beta- amyryn with 2V33

Figure: 5 Binding pose of Beta- amyryn with 5FC8

Figure: 6 Binding pose of Beta- amyryn with 5B1C.

Table: 2 Showing binding affinity between viral proteins and the Phytoconstituents:

S.NO	NAME OF THE COMPOUNDS	BINDING POSE WITH DOCKING ENERGY				
		kcal/mol PROTEINS				
		4M9K	3P54	2V33	5FC8	5B1C
1	Gallic acid	-6.5510	-6.5163	-6.4229	-6.4113	-6.5035
2.	Euphorbianin	-7.8760	-8.1123	-7.3056	-7.3221	-8.0150
3.	Leucocyanidol	-7.7395	-7.2542	-6.8735	-6.6955	-7.5619
4.	Quercitrin	-7.0235	-8.0103	-7.2866	-7.0884	-8.1170
5.	Quercitol	-4.8566	-4.7143	-4.5218	-4.7011	-4.7884
6.	Myricitrin	-6.8074	-6.5170	-6.3099	-4.2672	-4.3154
7.	3,4-di-O-Galloylquinic acid	-8.0913	-8.0103	-7.1586	-7.8097	-7.7119
8.	2,4,6-Tri-o-Galloyl-D-Glucose	-7.7947	-	-7.7714	-7.8569	-
9.	24-MethyleneCycloartenol	-11.592	-13.382	-11.729	-12.174	-12.420
10.	Beta-amyrin	-10.3035	-14.164	-6.3099	-12.460	-12.345

Active site Prediction:

The above results showed that Phyto-constituents of *Euphorbia hirta* were having the following Amino acid residues at the protein binding pocket which participate in the protein ligand interactions are Arg238 (E), Asp280 (E), Met883 (C), Lys240 (E), Arg315 (E), Tyr277 (E), Asn239 (E), Tyr492 (C), Lys537 (C), So4590 (A); Lys439 (A), Lys439 (A); Leu550 (C); Arg435 (A) Ser491 (C), Lys527 (C), Try492 (C), Lys439 (A), Leu550 (C) Arg435 (A), Gln340 (A), Lys442 (B), Thr444 (B), Lys436 (B), Lys438 (B), Tyr411 (B), Val443 (B), Lys442 (B), Phe312 (A), Asn197, Ser282, His214, Ala200, Phe201, Leu212, Val213, Ile270; Leu196, His214, Leu280, Ser75, His1060, Tyr1023, Lys1061, Glu1019, Arg55, Leu53, Ala56, Lle76, Leu95, Glu52, Leu53, Glu 54, Tyr1023.

CONCLUSION

In the present study, 10 chemical constituents were selected to dock against viral and dengue proteins. Among these compounds, six showed the best binding affinity. From these studies, it is inferred that the 24-MethyleneCycloartenol and 3,4-di-O-Galloylquinic acid was having the highest binding affinity and other constituents also has significant interaction with viral protein. This in-silico approach can be further investigated to generate more effective and potential drug through ligand based drug designing approaches. The above results demonstrated that Phyto-constituents of *Euphorbia hirta* can be suggested as potential drugs for viral and dengue diseases.

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